

Supplementary Materials

Subtraction of Temporally Sequential Digital Mammograms: Enhancing the Detection and Classification of Malignant Masses in Breast Imaging

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I. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Study Design and Data Collection

IN this retrospective study, 100 pairs of full-field digital mammograms were obtained from screenings conducted between 2016 and 2023, from different local healthcare facilities, including the Cyprus Population Screening Program in Aglantzia and Linopetra, Limassol, and Nicosia General Hospitals. The population included women 40 to 81 years of age (mean \pm standard deviation, 60.2 ± 9.6), with normal or benign (BI-RADS 1 & 2) mammograms in their first screening round. Their most recent mammograms contained either no masses (BI-RADS 1), benign masses (BI-RADS 2), or biopsy-confirmed malignant masses, with an average interval of 2.4 years between screenings. The normal population consisted of the BI-RADS 1 and BI-RADS 2 participants, while the participants associated with malignancies formed the malignant population. Ethical considerations were addressed, and the study received approval from the Institutional Review Board (Cyprus National Bioethics Committee). Informed consent forms were collected during the most recent screening round. This study was conducted in accordance with the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki.

Two mammographic views of the breast (Crano-Caudal (CC) and Medio-Lateral Oblique (MLO)) from two sequential screening rounds were collected from each participant, resulting in a total of 400 images. Two clinicians (C.N., radiologist with 27 years of experience, and A.Y., consultant breast surgeon with 10 years of experience) identified the eligible patients. Two radiologists (G.Sk. with 6 years of experience and E.O.V. with 5 years of experience), outlined the border of each mass for both BI-RADS benign and suspicious masses. Inter-observer agreement between the two radiologists was high, with an observed agreement of 97.41% and a Cohen's kappa of 0.95, indicating almost perfect reliability of the ground truth labels [1]. Discrepancies were resolved by consensus. Subsequently, suspicious cases were biopsied, followed by histopathological analysis, confirming their malignant nature. The biopsy confirmations were performed by each healthcare provider's pathology department, as per standard of care. The information was collected by a clinician and a researcher (A.C., academic medical oncologist with over 10 years of experience, and G.Sa., postgraduate researcher at the medical school with 5 years of experience).

Fifty percent of the population had none or benign findings in the first round of screening, and none or benign findings in the most recent mammogram (35 with no visible masses and 15 with only BI-RADS benign masses). Cases in which

benign findings emerged in the most recent screening with prior normal mammograms were included, along with cases in which benign findings appear both in prior and recent views, in order to investigate whether and how these findings evolved over time, ensuring effective analysis. The remaining 50% of the patients had normal or benign priors but at least one new biopsy-confirmed malignant mass in the most recent mammographic views. All prior mammograms had been reported as normal, with no traces of suspicious lesions, at the time of screening by the associated radiologists. This dataset included sequential mammographic images, precise annotations of each individual mass, which were used as a reference, and biopsy confirmations for the cases associated with suspicious masses. In total, 193 masses appeared, 90 BI-RADS benign (BI-RADS 2) and 103 biopsy-confirmed malignant. The dimensions of the mammographic images were 4096 x 3328 pixels in 8-bit DICOM format. This dataset is currently open-access (<https://zenodo.org/records/11446259>).

B. Breast Mass Segmentation and Detection

This study extends our previously published work [2], which focused on the detection and BI-RADS classification of micro-calcifications. In this study, breast masses –a different type of breast abnormality –were taken into consideration, and biopsy confirmations were added for the suspicious cases. The algorithm was enhanced, and various methodologies were extended and optimized for better performance. Fig. 1 demonstrates the proposed methodology for the diagnosis of BI-RADS benign and biopsy-confirmed malignant breast masses. To prepare the mammograms for the subsequent analysis, a series of pre-processing steps were implemented, including: normalization and the application of three sequential filtering techniques (Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE) [3], gamma correction [4], and border removal [5]).

Accurate registration is necessary to compensate for multiple factors affecting breast imaging, including variations in breast compression, alterations in breast shape, discrepancies in the presence of the pectoral muscle in the MLO view, and potential human errors occurring at the time of screening [6]. Demons registration [7], a nonrigid image alignment technique based on local deformations, was selected over other local and global registration techniques [8], due to its superior performance in terms of alignment accuracy. Specifically, the Demons and Affine registration techniques were evaluated and compared based on the residuals of the registration and subtraction process, which represent the sum of the remaining pixels after subtraction (Fig. 2). Demons demonstrated better overall shape

Fig. 1. Diagram of the proposed methodology.

Fig. 2. Plot comparing Affine and Demons registration based on the residuals of the subtraction, in logarithmic scale, for the four categories of breast density as defined by the BI-RADS. *BI-RADS*: Breast Imaging Reporting and Data System

alignment, with fewer residuals, while preserving the subtle changes between sequential mammograms. Therefore, Demons was selected as the most suitable method for this study, as it effectively accounted for the local and non-linear shape deformations of the breast. The two-stage registration process involved overall shape matching, followed by detailed, local registration. The prior mammographic view was registered to the most recent one, and then subtracted from the latter, effectively eliminating the overlapping regions that have remained unchanged between the screenings. The masses in the recent mammograms remained unaffected by the registration process, since it was the prior mammograms that were modified to align with the corresponding recent ones. The contrast ratio of the resulting subtracted image, calculated as the ratio of maximum to the average intensity, was compared to that of the recent mammographic view after pre-processing, to assess the effectiveness of temporal subtraction (Fig. 3). The subtracted image was further processed using unsharp mask filtering, a spatial filter that enhances a range of high frequencies [9].

The segmentation of masses was carried out in three steps: (1) thresholding, (2) application of morphological operations,

Fig. 3. Plot comparing the contrast ratio, in logarithmic scale, of the processed recent image and the image created by temporal subtraction, for the four categories of BI-RADS breast density. The contrast ratio increased in all cases, indicating that temporal subtraction was successful for all breast densities. *BI-RADS*: Breast Imaging Reporting and Data System

and (3) removal of periphery pixels. The process started with thresholding, which converted the image into a binary format, thereby eliminating low-intensity normal areas. The threshold value was determined through histogram analysis and optimization of the global classification rate during training. After the thresholding, morphological operations were applied to refine the binary image. Erosion was first used to eliminate isolated pixels that may have resulted from misalignment during registration or from thresholding artifacts. This operation was performed with a 2-pixel radius, smaller than the average size of masses, ensuring that adjacent regions were not unintentionally merged. Next, closing was applied using a 10-pixel radius to merge neighboring pixels and identify the constituents of each mass. This radius size was chosen after a comparison with the ground truth. In the final step, high-intensity regions at the periphery of the breast, which likely corresponded to the skin, were removed, as masses are not expected to form in that area. The border of the entire breast region was identified, allowing for the removal of all high-intensity regions along the border. The remaining regions were

TABLE I. Ranking of the features for the first classification round (normal vs. actual mass), using different feature selection techniques. The final selection, using the majority rule, is in bold.

t-test	MRMR	FI-ET	FI-RF	FI-XGB	SelectKBest	SFS	SBS
Corr. ¹ 90 D3	STD	Variance	Variance	Corr. 90 D1	Mean Intensity	Orientation	Area
Corr. 90 D2	Corr. Mean D1	STD	STD	Corr. Mean D2	STD	EN ⁶	ED
Corr. 0 D3	Corr. Mean D3	Smoothness	Smoothness	STD	Variance	ED	Perimeter
Corr. 45 D2	Corr. STD D1	Solidity	Solidity	Corr. Mean D3	Entropy	Solidity	Skewness
Corr. 135 D2	Corr. 0 D3	Mean Intensity	Mean Intensity	Corr. Mean D1	Corr. 45 D1	Extent	Con. 90 D1
Corr. 0 D2	Kurtosis	Corr. Mean D3	Extent	Solidity	Corr. 90 D1	Max Intensity	Con. Mean D1
Corr. Mean D1	Corr. 90 D2	Corr. 0 D2	Corr. Mean D2	Con. Mean D2	Corr. 135 D1	Skewness	Energy 135 D1
Con. ² Mean D3	Max Intensity	Corr. Mean D2	Corr. 0 D2	Area	Corr. Mean D1	STD	Con. STD D2
Con. 90 D3	Corr. 45 D2	Extent	Corr. Mean D3	Energy Mean D2	Energy 0 D1	Entropy	Corr. 45 D2
Con. 45 D3	Corr. 135 D2	Corr. Mean D1	Corr. 90 D2	Circularity	Energy Mean D1	Con. Mean D1	Corr. Mean D2
Con. 135 D3	Energy 135 D3	Energy 135 D1	Max Intensity	Homo. ⁵ Mean D1	Con. 45 D2	Corr. 0 D1	Homo. 135 D2
Corr. 45 D1	Corr. 45 D1	Max Intensity	Corr. 0 D1	Con. 45 D1	Con. 135 D2	Corr. 45 D1	Con. 90 D3
Corr. 45 D3	Corr. 90 D3	Corr. 45 D2	Corr. Mean D1	Con. STD D1	Con. Mean D2	Corr. 135 D1	Con. 135 D3
Corr. 135 D3	Corr. 0 D2	Corr. 90 D2	MiAL ³	Extent	Corr. 0 D2	Energy 90 D1	Corr. 90 D3
Corr. 135 D1	Entropy	Corr. 90 D3	Shape Ratio	MiAL	Corr. 45 D2	Corr. 0 D3	Homo. 0 D3
Con. 0 D3	Corr. 135 D1	Corr. 135 D2	Corr. 90 D1	Con. 135 D2	Corr. 90 D2	Corr. Mean D3	Circularity
Con. 45 D2	Corr. 135 D3	Corr. 45 D1	Corr. 90 D3	Con. Mean D1	Corr. 135 D2	Energy 0 D3	Shape Ratio
Con. 135 D2	Corr. Mean D2	Energy Mean D2	Corr. 0 D3	Perimeter	Corr. Mean D2		Breast Density
Con. Mean D2	Mean Intensity	Corr. 0 D1	ED ⁴	Energy 135 D2	Con. 0 D3		
Corr. 90 D1	Solidity	Area	Corr. 135 D1	Corr. 90 D2	Con. 45 D3		

¹Corr.: Correlation ²Con.: Contrast ³MiAL: Minor Axis Length ⁴ED: Equivalent Diameter ⁵Homo.: Homogeneity ⁶Euler Number

TABLE II. Ranking of the features for the second classification round (BI-RADS benign vs. biopsy-confirmed malignant masses), using different feature selection techniques. The final selection, using the majority rule, is in bold.

t-test	MRMR	FI-ET	FI-RF	SelectKBest	SFS	SBS
Area	Area	Area	Area	Area	MaAL	Area
MaAL ¹	MaAL	MaAL	MaAL	MaAL	Orientation	MaAL
MiAL ²	MiAL	MiAL	MiAL	MiAL	Solidity	MiAL
Convex Area	Convex Area	Convex Area	Convex Area	Convex Area	Extent	Filled Area
Filled Area	Euler Number	Filled Area	Filled Area	Filled Area	Perimeter	ED
ED ³	ED	ED	ED	ED	Mean Intensity	Perimeter
Solidity	Extent	Solidity	Extent	Solidity	Min Intensity	Max Intensity
Extent	Perimeter	Extent	Perimeter	Extent	Max Intensity	Con. 0 D1
Perimeter	Max Intensity	Perimeter	Correlation 45 D1	Perimeter	STD	Con. 45 D1
Corr. ⁴ 0 D2	Corr. 0 D1	Corr. 0 D2	Energy STD D1	Corr. 0 D2	Variance	Con. 90 D1
Corr. 45 D2	Corr. STD D2	Corr. 45 D2	Corr. 0 D2	Corr. 45 D2	Con. ⁶ 0 D1	Con. Mean D1
Corr. 135 D2	Energy STD D2	Corr. 135 D2	Corr. 135 D2	Corr. 135 D2	Con. 45 D1	Corr. 45 D1
Corr. Mean D2	Homo. ⁵ 45 D2	Corr. Mean D2	Corr. STD D2	Corr. Mean D2	Con. 90 D2	Energy 90 D1
Corr. STD D2	Corr. 0 D3	Homo. STD D2	Corr. 0 D3	Corr. STD D2	Breast Density	Con. 0 D2
Corr. 0 D3	Corr. 45 D3	Corr. 0 D3	Corr. 45 D3	Corr. 0 D3	Age	Energy Mean D2
Corr. 45 D3	Corr. 135 D3	Corr. 45 D3	Corr. 135 D3	Corr. 45 D3		Energy 45 D3
Corr. 90 D3	Corr. Mean D3	Corr. 135 D3	Corr. Mean D3	Corr. 90 D3		Corr. 135 D3
Corr. 135 D3	Circularity	Corr. Mean D3	Circularity	Corr. 135 D3		Shape Ratio
Corr. Mean D3	Compactness	Circularity	Compactness	Corr. Mean D3		
Circularity	Age	Shape Ratio	Shape Ratio	Circularity		

¹MaAL: Major Axis Length ²MiAL.: Minor Axis Length ³ED: Equivalent Diameter ⁴Corr.: Correlation ⁵Homo: Homogeneity ⁶Con: Contrast

then considered as potential masses or ROIs.

C. Feature Extraction and Selection for Classification

Numerous features were extracted from every segmented ROI to first separate the actual masses from the falsely segmented normal tissue and then classify the masses as benign or malignant using various classifiers. In total, 98 features were extracted, including 2 epidemiological and 96 image characteristics (shape-based, intensity-based, first-order statistics (FOS), and gray level co-occurrence matrix (GLCM) features) [10], [11]. Feature extraction was performed using

MATLAB 2024b. For each segmented ROI, a feature vector consisting of 98 values was generated. The epidemiological features considered included the age at the time of the most recent mammograms and BI-RADS breast density. Regarding the GLCM features, each was derived at 0, 45, 90, and 135 degrees, along with the mean and standard deviation (STD), i.e., 24 values for each different offset D ($D_1 = 5$, $D_2 = 15$, and $D_3 = 25$ pixels).

However, not all of these features contributed to the classification and diagnosis and, therefore, had to be removed from the process. To identify the most relevant features, a

Fig. 4. Classification results of the detected regions as normal tissue or masses, using different classifiers and cross-validation methods. *LDA*: Linear Discriminant Analysis; *k-NN*: k-Nearest Neighbors; *SVM*: Support Vector Machine; *RF*: Random Forest; *MLP*: Multi-Layer Perceptron; *ADA*: Adaboost; *BAG*: Bagging; *GB*: Gradient Boosting; *ANN*: Artificial Neural Network; *LOPO*: Leave-One-Patient-Out

Fig. 5. Classification results of the masses as BI-RADS benign or biopsy-confirmed malignant, using different classifiers and cross-validation methods. *LDA*: Linear Discriminant Analysis; *k-NN*: k-Nearest Neighbors; *SVM*: Support Vector Machine; *RF*: Random Forest; *MLP*: Multi-Layer Perceptron; *ADA*: Adaboost; *BAG*: Bagging; *GB*: Gradient Boosting; *ANN*: Artificial Neural Network; *LOPO*: Leave-One-Patient-Out

combination of eight feature selection methods was employed, which included: (1) t-test, (2) Maximum Relevance-Minimum Redundancy (MRMR), (3) Feature Importance using Extra Trees (FI-ET), (4) Feature Importance using Random Forest (FI-RF), (5) Feature Importance using XGBoost (FI-XGB), (6) SelectKBest, (7) Sequential Forward Selection (SFS), and (8) Sequential Backward Selection (SBS) [12]–[14]. This ensemble approach reduces the dependency on any single ranking criterion, thereby mitigating potential bias and improving the reliability of classification compared to individual methods. Scores were generated for each feature using methods (1) to (6), and the top 20 features with the highest scores were

selected to streamline the procedure and avoid unnecessary complexity. To further optimize the feature set, SFS and SBS were used to assess classification performance using different subsets of the selected features, again optimized to identify the 20 features with the highest performance. A majority-rule approach was applied to consolidate the results across all methods, and features common to at least three techniques were retained for the final feature set (Tables I & II). This approach was selected to ensure that only the most significant features were included, and the potential for bias in the selection process was minimized by relying on multiple independent feature selection methods. All feature selection techniques were

applied only to the training set, to avoid bias.

D. Training and Comparison of Classifier Models

For the classification, nine classifiers were evaluated including: Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) [15], k-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN) [16], Support Vector Machine (SVM) [17], Random Forest (RF) [18], Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) [19], Adaboost (ADA) [20], Bagging (BAG) [21], Gradient Boosting (GB) [22], and ensemble voting [20]. In the case of k-NN, various nearest neighbor values (1, 3, 5, 7, 9, and 11) were tested to identify the optimal configuration. For SVM, various kernel functions were evaluated, such as linear, polynomial, and Radial Basis Function (rbf). The ensemble voting method was subject to evaluation in both hard and soft schemes. Furthermore, several artificial neural network (ANN) [16] architectures were tested, with network parameters fine-tuned based on validation loss and accuracy. The tuning process involved adjusting key hyperparameters, including batch size, learning rate, number of hidden layers, number of neurons per layer, activation functions, and optimizers. The optimal configuration was determined by systematically evaluating different parameter combinations to achieve the best classification performance during training. In total, more than 20 classifiers were initially evaluated for the classification. The classifiers demonstrating the most robust performance were selected for detailed analysis. These included a mix of linear, nonlinear, and ensemble methods to provide a comprehensive benchmark across different learning paradigms.

The classifiers were trained and tested using two validation approaches: LOPO and k-fold-patient Cross-Validation (CV). In both cases, validation per patient is crucial and necessary to avoid bias from the inclusion of images from the same patient in both the training and test sets and artificially improve the algorithm's accuracy. In both LOPO and k-fold CV, each patient's data were exclusively assigned to either the training or test set, eliminating any overlap between the two. Additionally, each mass was treated independently, as the MLO and CC views capture it from different angles, potentially leading to distinct feature representations and classifications. This approach is equivalent to radiological evaluation, where, in some cases, even the radiologists cannot identify the mass in both views. In two consecutive classification rounds, the falsely detected regions were first eliminated, and then the masses were classified as BI-RADS benign or biopsy-confirmed malignant. To address class imbalance, the synthetic minority oversampling technique (SMOTE) was employed [23]. SMOTE works by generating synthetic instances of the minority class by interpolating between existing minority samples in the feature space. When training the model, SMOTE generated synthetic samples of the minority class, whether benign or malignant, based on the training data available for each fold. This ensured that the classifier was not biased toward the majority class. The process was repeated each time during CV, adjusting the balance based on the data of the patient left out in each iteration. This technique allowed for a more robust model capable of handling the class imbalance while training on a balanced dataset at every step.

The classification performance was assessed by computing key evaluation metrics, including sensitivity, specificity, accuracy, and the AUC. Optimal cutoff values were chosen to minimize FP and False Negative (FN) instances.

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